

Defining a New Digital Twin Ontology for Cultural Heritage Preservation – the Case of ARGUS

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Abstract

The sustainable preservation of cultural heritage (CH) assets increasingly demands predictive monitoring approaches that integrate multimodal data and decision support mechanisms. EU project ARGUS introduces a semantic ontology designed to unify sensor observations, diagnostic activities, risk predictions, and conservation decisions within a coherent, operational framework. Building upon standards such as CIDOC CRM, SOSA/SSN, PROV-O, GeoSPARQL, and OWL-Time, the ontology advances heritage computing toward dynamic condition monitoring and preventive conservation strategies.

CCS Concepts

• **Information systems** → **Ontology modeling**; • **Theory of computation** → **Knowledge representation and reasoning**;

1. Introduction

Cultural heritage (CH) assets are increasingly at risk from environmental, anthropogenic, and structural factors. Effective preservation demands proactive strategies based not only on static documentation, but on dynamic, multimodal, and predictive monitoring approaches. While established ontologies such as CIDOC CRM [Doe03] provide robust models for static heritage descriptions, they lack constructs for real-time condition tracking, risk forecasting, and decision support.

The ARGUS project (Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement No. 101132308) addresses this gap by developing an integrated framework for remote monitoring, digital twin creation, and predictive management of cultural heritage sites. Within ARGUS, we introduce **PANOPTES**, a new digital twin ontology designed to semantically integrate sensor observations, diagnostic processes, risk predictions, and conservation decisions into a unified, operational model.

PANOPTES builds upon standards such as SOSA/SSN [JHC*19] (sensor observations), PROV-O [MM13] (provenance tracking), GeoSPARQL [PH12] (spatial modeling), and OWL-Time [HP06] (temporal representation), while maintaining compatibility with CIDOC CRM principles for cultural heritage description. Recent work on semantic models for heritage digital twins [FN25] highlights the critical need for predictive, dynamic, and multimodal representations, further motivating the development of integrated frameworks such as PANOPTES. Through this integration, PANOPTES enables the evolution of cultural heritage management from reactive documentation to predictive, evidence-based conservation planning.

2. PANOPTES Ontology Overview

PANOPTES models the complete dynamic preservation workflow, structured around the following core entities:

- **Asset**: A cultural heritage entity, modeled as a specialization of `sosa:FeatureOfInterest` and `geo:Feature`.
- **Measurement**: A specialization of `sosa:Observation`, capturing spatiotemporal data about asset condition.
- **Instrument**: Devices or methods (`sosa:Sensor`) used to perform Measurements.
- **Diagnosis**: An interpretation of Measurement data, modeled as a `prov:Activity`, assessing asset conditions.
- **Prediction**: A forecasted outcome (`prov:Entity`) derived from computational models based on Diagnoses.
- **Threat**: A risk factor potentially impacting an Asset, semantically linked to spatial and temporal contexts.
- **Decision**: An action planning outcome, governed by Policies and Rules, to mitigate predicted risks.
- **Cultural Documentation**: Structured records of observations, diagnoses, and interventions, following `cidoc-crm:E31_Document`.

Spatial properties are represented using GeoSPARQL [PH12], while temporal evolution is modeled using OWL-Time [HP06]. Provenance tracking of all observations, computations, and decisions is ensured through PROV-O [MM13].

2.1 Ontological Relations

PANOPTES defines a rich set of semantic relations among its core entities, structuring the dynamic monitoring and decision-making process:

- **Asset** is observed through one or more **Measurements**, each linked to specific **Instruments** and executed following a defined **Protocol**.
- **Measurement** produces a **Quantity** result and is characterized by spatial (`geo:Geometry`) and temporal (`time:Instant`) attributes.
- **Measurement** data are interpreted via a **Diagnosis**, representing an analytic activity that assesses the Asset's condition over time.
- **Diagnosis** is generated using a **Computational Model**, which encapsulates methods for condition inference or deterioration assessment.
- **Diagnosis** informs a **Prediction**, modeling expected future states or risks impacting the Asset.
- **Prediction** is linked to specific **Threats**, which are categorized according to their origin (e.g., environmental, structural, anthropogenic).
- **Threats** are associated with potential **Events** (e.g., structural failure, environmental stress episodes) that may require urgent intervention.
- **Decision** entities are informed by Diagnoses and Predictions, following **Policies** and detailed **Rules** that regulate conservation strategies.
- **Policy** defines general conservation goals, while **Rules** specify operational thresholds, actions, or mitigation procedures.
- **Visualization** entities are linked to **Computational Models** and Predictions to facilitate stakeholder understanding through graphical interfaces.
- **Cultural Documentation** maintains provenance records, linking Observations, Diagnoses, Predictions, Decisions, and conservation Events back to their originating Assets.
- Each **Event** can retroactively update the Asset's state and trigger new Measurements, closing the monitoring-feedback loop.

Through these relations, PANOPTES creates a dynamic semantic graph capturing not only the static features of cultural heritage assets but also their evolving conditions, inferred risks, and managed interventions over time.

2.2 Design Principles

PANOPTES is founded on the following design principles:

- **Asset-Centric Modeling**: All activities are linked to specific cultural assets.
- **Dynamic State Representation**: Support for temporal evolution and condition monitoring.
- **Predictive Maintenance Integration**: Formal representation of forecasts and interventions.
- **Semantic Interoperability**: Alignment with CIDOC CRM, SOSA/SSN [JHC*19], PROV-O, GeoSPARQL, and OWL-Time standards.
- **Operational Readiness**: Natural mapping to a relational database schema for scalable deployment.

3. Pilot Deployment within ARGUS

PANOPTES is piloted within the European Union's ARGUS project (Grant Agreement No. 101132308), focusing on proactive conservation of at-risk heritage sites.

Two primary pilot scenarios are under development:

- **Structural Monitoring**: Continuous acquisition of structural deformation measurements (e.g., crack width monitoring) for historical monuments. Measurements are semantically linked to assets, diagnoses infer deterioration trends, and predictions forecast risk escalation.
- **Environmental Risk Monitoring**: Integration of environmental sensor data (temperature, humidity, pollutants) inside museums and historical structures. Diagnoses detect unfavorable microclimatic conditions, while predictions guide preventive interventions to mitigate material degradation.

PANOPTES supports real-time data ingestion, dynamic updates of asset states, and traceable decision-making workflows aimed at minimizing deterioration risks.

4. Conclusion and Future Work

PANOPTES advances the state of the art in cultural heritage management by bridging static documentation models with predictive monitoring and decision support. Through its integration of multimodal data streams, predictive analytics, and conservation planning into a coherent semantic framework, it enables a shift from reactive to proactive heritage preservation strategies.

Future work will focus on scaling deployment across diverse heritage asset types, extending semantic models to support AI-driven risk assessment techniques, and enhancing visualization tools to facilitate stakeholder interaction with digital twins.

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